

**DEGREES OF EQUIVALENCE IN TRANSLATION –
A CASE STUDY OF NEPALI NOVEL ‘SETO BAGH’
INTO ENGLISH AS ‘THE WAKE OF THE WHITE TIGER’**

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Abstract:

This research paper was conducted to investigate the degrees of equivalence while translating a Nepali Novel ‘*Seto Bagh*’ into English as ‘*The Wake of the White Tiger*’. Both versions of the novel were used as the sources of data to find out how it was tried to get optimum degree of equivalence. The qualitative data were used with survey design and later they were analyzed. Fifty cultural terms were randomly selected from the novel named ‘*The Wake of The White Tiger*’ and ‘*Seto Bagh*’ and analyzed in it. Among six degrees of equivalence, mostly the optimum degree of equivalence found to be used. The partial, poor and zero equivalents are also found to some extent. Literal translation, sense translation, definition, substitution and transliteration are also used in it.

Keywords: translation, source language, target language, literal translation, transliteration

1. Introduction

This research paper explores the degrees of equivalence in translation, comparing two versions of a Nepali historical novel ‘*Seto Bagh*’ which was translated as ‘*The Wake of The White Tiger*’ into English. Cultural terms in translated version are analyzed to confirm the equivalence with original ones.

1.1 Background of the Study

Translation is the process of converting the messages from one language to another language. It always includes two languages and two cultures, and it is a process of changing speech or written text from one language to another. Translation process produces a text in target language from source language. Newmark (1998, p.5) has defined translation as rendering the meaning of a text into another language in the way that the author intended the text. It is commonly understood that translation should be simple so that someone ought to be able to say something as well in one language as into another. Riccardi (2010, p.86) says, “*The*

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translated text is well anchored in the target culture and, in transposing the original; the translator will often be confronted with culture-bound expressions or situations." This indicates that the equivalence is one of the most important aspects or goals of translation; translator has to focus on searching the best equivalent terms between two different languages or dialects. Catford (1965, p. 27) defined translation equivalence as *"an empirical phenomena, discovered by comparing source language (SL) and target language (TL) texts or underlying conditions, or justification of translation equivalence"*.

English language is the language of globalized world, mass media, print media, official instruction and education in many countries of the world. That is the reason why translation into English from other languages of every fields getting popularity. The concept and cultural terms of one language cannot be found in another language. So, perfect translation is impossible but good translation is always desirable.

The translator should try the best technique of bridging the gaps between the languages.

'Seto Bagh' is Nepali historical as well as popular novel, which was written by Diamond Shumshare Rana, and was published in 2030 BS for the first time. Greta Rana has translated the novel into English in 1984 as 'The Wake of the White Tiger'. As can be thought in the novel by Diamond Shumshare Rana (2016), the novel revolves around the life of the Jagat Jung Rana, the eldest son of Janga Bahadur Rana. The plot is set around the time when Janga Bahadur Rana was in power and after his demise. It has been translated into French, English, Japanese languages. This novel has shown the real picture of Nepali political situation during the time of Rana regime when they were completely autocratic towards the general people and Nepalese people were revolting for freedom along with monarchy.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

This study had the following objectives:

- a) To find out the degrees of equivalence of cultural terms between Nepali text 'Seto Bagh' and English translated version 'The Wake of The White Tiger'.
- b) To find out the techniques used in translation.

1.3 Research Questions

This research conducted with the following questions.

- a) What are the degrees of equivalence of cultural terms between Nepali text 'Seto Bagh' and English translated version 'The Wake of The White Tiger'?
- b) What are the techniques used in translating these cultural words?

1.4 Significance of the Study

This research paper will help the translation practitioners to translate different texts with optimum degree of equivalence. They can choose right techniques of translation to produce most approximate texts.

1.5 Delimitations of the Study

This study was delimited to the historical Nepali novel 'Seto Bagh' and its translated version 'The Wake of the White Tiger'. And it was delimited to only the cultural words used in the novel Seto Bāgh and it only aimed to see the translation equivalence.

2. Review of Literature

There are significant numbers of texts that have been translated from English language to Nepali and vice versa. Many researchers have carried out the studies on translation.

Gautam (2008) conducted a study entitled 'A study on Techniques and Gaps of Translation of Cultural Terms: A Case of Prahalād'. The main objectives of the research were to identify and classify the cultural terms into different categories, to find out the techniques employed in the translation of Nepali cultural terms into the English version, to find out the frequency of the different techniques of translation, to find out the gaps in the translation process.

Raut (2010) carried out a research study on 'Bridging Cultural Gaps in Translation: A Case of The Novel Alikhit'. The main objectives of the study were to identify and categorize the Nepali cultural terms used in the novel *Alikhit*, to find out the techniques of bridging the cultural gaps in translation.

Shrestha (2011) conducted a research on 'Techniques of Translating Culture: A Case of Sani's Valour.' His main objectives of the study were to find out the techniques employed in the translating cultural terms used in the children nove Saniko Sahas, to find out the frequencies of different techniques used in translation.

Tamang (2012) conducted the research study on 'Techniques in Translation of Cultural Terms: A Case of novel Siddhartha'. His main objectives were to find out the techniques and their frequency employed in translating English cultural terms into Nepali version of the novel Siddhartha.

Dahal (2016) conducted a research on the title 'Degree of Equivalence: A Case of Shirisko Phool'. The main objectives of the study were to find out the degrees of equivalence of cultural terms between Nepali and English version, to identify and classify the cultural terms used in the novel Shirisko Phool in both source and target text and to find out techniques used in translation and identify their contribution in degrees of equivalence of cultural terms between Nepali and English versions of the novel Shirisko Phool.

Joshi (2014) conducted a research on 'Loss of Meaning in Translation: A Case of Seto Bagh'. His main objectives of the study were to explore the causes of meaning loss of social and cultural terms in translation of the novel 'Seto Bagh' at word and phrase level, to explore the ways to compensate the meaning gap in translation.

After reviewing the afro-mentioned research works, this researcher found the gap in research over the translation of the novel 'Seto Bagh'. The concept of degree of equivalence is not touched by the previous researchers. So, it became a new concept for the research and this paper is focused on the untouched and undiscovered issue of the novel.

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1 Translation and Translation Studies

Translation is considered as a bilingual activity in which the meaning of a piece of language is rendered into another language. Since two languages are involved in every piece of translation work, a translator stands as a mediator between two distinct languages.

Translation is cultural, referential as well as linguistic and stylistic activity between two languages or dialects of the same. There are many types of texts to be translated such as literary, technical, academic, and non-literary and so on. Newmark (1998, p.5) defines "Translation is a process of rendering the meaning of a text into another language in the way that the author intended the text." It means translation is the general term referring to the transfer of thoughts and ideas from one language (source) to another (target), whether the languages are in written or in oral form; whether the languages have established orthographies or do not have such standardization; or whether one or both language is based on signs, as with sign language of the deaf. This definition is regarded as the broadest definition.

On the other hand, from cultural point of view, translation is less linguistic and more and even exclusively; a cultural process as it is said "one does not translate language but culture." Snell-Hornby (1988, as cited in Awasthi, J. R., Bhattarai G. R. & Khaniya T. R. (2014, p.12) puts "Translation, in many cases, is directed by the culture than the language because culture shapes language and language shapes reality." It shows that the success of good translation depends on the gaps between SL culture and TL culture where a translator should always try to bridge the gaps. To give illumination, the Nepali culture specific words, likejan āi, tūppi, and bratābāndā are senseless to translate into.

English language since they do not have equivalent terms in English language. Similarly, while observing translation from overall perspectives, translation is nothing but a procedure that leads from a written SLT to an optimally equivalent TLT and requires the syntactic, semantic, stylistic, and text- pragmatic comprehension by the translator of the original text. Translation is both linguistic and cultural activity and the translator has to consider the context, the rules of grammar of languages, their writing convention idioms and cultures. Translator should establish a relationship of equivalence between SLT and TLT.

3.2 Types of Translation

As there are various types of translation, it is necessary to deal with major types of it. We need to discuss the mostly used category i.e. text-based translation. Apart from this, Roman Jakobson's study of translation equivalence gave new impetus to the theoretical analysis of translation since he introduced the notion of "equivalence in difference". On his article 'On Linguistic Aspects of Translation', he distinguishes three types of translation. (as cited in Bassnett, 1980, p.22)

- a) intralingual (within one language, i.e. rewording or paraphrase),
- b) interlingual (between two languages),
- c) intersemiotic (between sign systems).

3.3 Techniques of Translation

Translation is the process of maintaining the nearest equivalent text from one language to another. It is always a challenging job for a translator due to the dissimilarities between languages. To get this goal to some extent, s/he should use some techniques of translation. The use of proper techniques depends on the intuition and decision of translators various scholars have recommended several techniques of translation.

Awasthi, J. R., Bhattarai G. R. & Khaniya T. R. (2014, p. 111) provides the following techniques for compensating gaps in translation:

- a) transliteration,
- b) transliteration plus explanation,
- c) transference,
- d) replace the cultural expressions of the source text with those of the target language.

In a similar way, Newmark (1998, p.103) summarizes twelve translation procedures.

- a) transference,
- b) cultural equivalent,
- c) neutralization,
- d) literal translation,
- e) label,
- f) naturalization,
- g) componential analysis,
- h) deletion,
- i) couplet,
- j) accepted standard translation,
- k) paraphrase, gloss, notes, etc.,
- l) classifier.

From above mentioned lists, we can infer that a number of techniques or procedures of translation are applied to compensate the linguistic, cultural and extra-linguistic gaps. Especially, regarding cultural gaps, no single technique can be absolutely correct and complete to reach a perfect translation. Thus, a good translator may have to use a lot of techniques as per necessity. Here, some common techniques of translation frequently used are briefly discussed and examples are derived.

3.3.1 Literal Translation

Literal translation is a simple and easy technique of translation. It is also known as word for word or exact translation. It is mostly and widely used technique of translation. Literal translation occurs whenever word-for-word replacement is possible without breaking rules in TL.

3.3.2 Borrowing / Transference

The technique of translation in which words from source language to target language are taken to bridge gap is called borrowing. It is also called transference. Loan translation and

transliteration come under this process. If TL lacks the concept of SL, the same word is transferred to TL by just changing alphabets into target language.

3.3.3 Substitution

Substitution refers to the use of similar word in target language instead of using the real source word. This technique is useful when there are concepts which overlap each other with similar sense. Except in the cases of clear-cut presence versus absence of a particular concept, the text may lose the flavor of originality of both the SLT and TLT.

3.3.4 Paraphrasing / Definition

The SL terms are extended or defined to make it simpler in this technique. It is also termed as paraphrasing. Some unknown terms are simplified and made clear in the context though many words are used in place of single term. It is employed when there is absence of particular specified word for the concept in TL. While paraphrasing the SL term into the TL the translator's attempt is to give descriptive and functional equivalence of the SL terms.

3.3.5 Elaboration / Addition

It is also called addition. If some expression or terms are not enough to convey the intended meaning of SLT to TLT, then translator has to add or elaborate some terms which is called elaboration. The translator gives some additional information of the cultural terms of SLT by the use of some suitable addition from the cultural available in TLT.

3.3.6 Blending

Blending refers to the words which are coined through borrowing one of the constituents from SL or donor language and reproducing or translating the other constituent of the construction. It is also called fusion. The part of SL word is combined with a part of TL word. In this technique, we can find the fusion of two words. The examples of Nepali cultural terms and their English equivalent words can be listed as below;

3.3.7 Sense Translation

Translator sometimes translates only the sense of the cultural words to transfer the meaning in TL. If the SL structure is complex, words used in a text are redundant and their translations mislead the meaning, it is better just to translate the sense (meaning). Here, one term gives sense only but not the exact meaning.

3.3.8 Mistranslation

Mistranslation is a procedure in which the translator makes an attempt but the wrong to translate the SL terms. Here, the TL word is not translated as the sense of SL and problems occur. The Nepali sentence and its English

3.4 Equivalence in Translation

The term equivalence refers to the sameness, similarity or correspondence between SLT and TLT in terms of form and meaning. Equivalence can be observed at various levels in linguistic units. Generally, lexical equivalence collocation and idiomatic equivalence, syntactic equivalence, pragmatic equivalence and textual equivalence are some general types. Lexical equivalence is the most basic level of equivalence. It is also called word-level of equivalence.

Bayer (2007) as cited in Awasthi, J. R., Bhattarai G. R. & Khaniya T. R. (2014, pp.103-105) divides equivalence into six degrees. They are optimum translation, near-optimum translation, partial translation, poor translation, zero translation and mistranslation.

4. Methods and Procedures of the Study

4.1 Design and Method of the Study

By applying the survey method, this research process was conducted. Two version of the same novel were surveyed in it.

4.2 Population, Sample and Sampling Strategy

The Fifteen cultural terms used in Nepali text '*Seto Bagh*' and its English translated version '*The Wake of the White Tiger*' were the population for this study. The researcher selected fifteen cultural terms used in the novels by adopting purposive non-random sampling strategy where researcher grouped all the fifty categorically into five categories namely ecological, material, social, religious and conceptual based on their existence.

4.3 Research Tools

Survey can be accomplished using different tools of data collection. The researcher used observation as a main tool for data collection. The researcher read and reread the Nepali book '*Seto Bagh*' and English version of the novel '*The Wake of the White Tiger*' in order to observe the levels of equivalence and find out techniques of translation. Two dictionaries namely *Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary* (8th ed.) and *Ekata Comprehensive Nep -Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) were consulted for the determination of the degrees of equivalence by comparing the contrastive meanings of both SL and TL terms.

4.4 Sources of Data (Primary and Secondary)

The researcher used secondary sources of data as the source of data for the study. Both versions of the novel, Nepali book '*Seto Bagh*' and translated English book '*The Wake of the White Tiger*' were read by the researcher in order to observe the level of equivalence and find out the techniques of translation that contributed to the achievement of optimum translation equivalence.

4.5 Data Collection Procedures

Then, the researcher read the text and encircled the cultural words in the English version of the novel. After that, the researcher repeatedly read the Nepali version of the novel to find out

the equivalent words of those cultural terms. Next, the researcher listed out fifteen cultural terms in his notebook from whole of the novel first from original Nepali version then, their equivalent terms from the translated English version of the novel.

4.6 Data Analysis and Interpretation Procedures

The collected data were gathered, recorded, analyzed, interpreted, and presented with the help of the appropriate statistical tools such as tables, charts and using interpretative and descriptive procedures. The particular cultural words and their English equivalent were compared on the basis of meaning given in the dictionaries and the meaning they convey to their respective readers and the degrees of equivalence were determined with the help of dictionaries

5. Analysis and Interpretation of the Results

After the collection of data, the data were classified in to five categories; they were ecological terms, social terms, material terms, religious terms and conceptual terms by giving the contextual sentences were also used in the table of each categorical criterion. Each term of both versions was analyzed on the basis of dictionary meaning and the context they were used in. With the rigorous study and interpretation, the degree of equivalence was determined.

Only five degrees of equivalence except mistranslation were used to fall the words under them. At the same time, the techniques of translation were also analyzed by comparing the meanings of both languages with the help of *Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary* (8th ed.) and *Ekta Comprehensive Nep- Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) out. At last, the contribution of those applied techniques was also analyzed in terms of six degrees of equivalence.

5.1 Classification of Cultural Terms

The cultural terms which were selected from the novel were classified into five categories. They are: ecology, material culture, social culture, religious culture and conceptual term. All purposively selected fifteen terms were classified into the following cultural categories. They are as follows:

5.1.1 Ecology

Ecology refers to the geographical features which are bound to the specific culture such as mountain, animals, hills, plants, wind, seasons, rivers weather conditions, lakes, forests, sea and fields. It is the combination of living and nonliving things in the environment.

Three ecological terms selected from the novel '*Seto Bagh*' and their equivalent terms in English are follows;

Table 1: Ecological Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>tudikhel</i>	<i>Jagatlai voli tudikhelma garne thupraikam banki thiyo. (p.6)</i>	Parādegound	Jagat worked at parade ground and next morning he went out of he went out of chamber. (p.6)

Here, SL term *tudikhel* has the meaning as “parade ground”. Similarly, the term “parade ground” means a place where soldiers gather to march or to be inspected by an officer or an important visitor. On the other hand, *tudikhel* has English equivalence in *Ekta Comprehensive Nep -Eng dictionary*(1st ed.) as parade ground and therefore, the TL term “parade ground” is optimally equivalent with the SL term *tudikhel* and the translator has used literal translation as a technique.

Table 2: Ecological Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>hirā</i>	<i>Sunkhip jutta ra hirāko tak haliako sunaulo buttedar ackan thiyo. (p.97)</i>	diamond	He had diamond studded buttons and a jeweled broach at his breast. (p.82)

The word *hirā* means a glimmering glass like mineral having a lot of precious value in comparison to other minerals. *Hirā* is the equivalent term of “diamond” according to the *Ekta Comprehensive Nep- Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) and the TL term “diamond” means a clear precious stone of pure carbon, the hardest substance known. So, it is optimum translation and literal technique of translation has been used as technique of translation.

Table 3: Ecological Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>Pahād</i>	<i>Rajkanyalai pahād prasthān garnūthlyo. (p. 59).</i>	Hill	Actually there were no toads at all in the eastern hill. (p. 49).

Here, the SL term *pahād* means higher land in comparison to the land around it. *The Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary* (8th ed.) defines “hill” as an area of land that is higher than the land around it but not as high as a mountain. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep- Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) also provides the equivalent term of *pahād* as hill. So, it is optimum translation and the translator has literal technique of translation.

5.1.2 Material Culture

Material culture refers to the things which are made by human beings and are famous within a particular society and culture. Generally, it includes foods, clothes, houses and towns, transport, ornaments and monuments. Ten material terms selected from the novel *Seto Bagh* and their equivalent terms in English.

Table 4: Material Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	Mūdrā	<i>Nepālko mallakalin mudra Tibetko bajarma prayog hunthyo. p.3)</i>	Currency	Tibetans used to accept Nepalese currency for all normal business transactions. (p.3)

The term mudra means money. TL term “currency” means system of money that a country uses. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep- Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) gives its equivalent as coin, piece of money. Here, the translation is near optimum degree because piece of money is not exact to system of money that a country uses. As a technique, the translator has used substitution translation.

Table 5: Material Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>Vojankachya</i>	<i>Rāj āraṅI ra pradh ānmantri vojankachya puge. (p.139)</i>	Banqueting Hall	When they entered the banqueting hall, an assembled had put away liquor (p.117)

The term vojanakacha means place for meal. TL term banqueting hall refers a hall for formal meal for a large number of people, usually for a special Occasion, at which speeches are often made. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep- Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) provides the equivalent term as kitchen or hotel. So, it is partial translation and the translator has used definition as a translation technique.

Table 6: Material Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>Sisi</i>	<i>France ko emperorle Jungabhadur laai sisi diyaka thiya. (p.122)</i>	Bottles	Emperor of France had presented Junga Bahadur bottles. (p107)

The SL term *sisi* means glass ware or mirror. The TL term “bottles” mean glass or plastic container, usually round with straight sides and a narrow neck, used especially for storing liquids. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep-Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) also provides the equivalent term as bottle. So, it is optimum degree of translation and literal technique of translation has been used.

5.1.3 Social Culture and Organization

The term associated with social culture is specific to the particular cultural periphery. There is relationship between social organization and the people living in that society. Different societies have different terms to refer to organizations, customs and procedures and so on. The social culture includes work and leisure, social customs, procedures, activities, politics, administrations, legal activities and historical facts. Ten social cultural and organizational terms selected from the novel '*Seto Bagh*' and their equivalent terms with context in English are as follows;

Table 7: Social Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	Samarthan	<i>Ani birele pani Chandrako salhahalai pani samarthan agre.(p,920</i>	Agreement	Bir noded his agreement for him too.(p,77)

The term *samarthan* means consent between two person, parties or institutions. The TL term “agreement” refers an understanding between entities to follow a specific course of conduct. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep-Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) provides the equivalent term as arrangement or agreement. So, it is optimum degree of translation and translator has used literal translation.

Table 8: Social Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>Sapat</i>	<i>Birle dhani ya garib natahos ya pariwarko sablai khatam garchhu vanera sapat liyo. (p.84)</i>	Oath	It was oath to destroy the wealthy even if belong to his own family or love him. (p.71)

The SL term *sapat* is a term in Nepali which refers to formal promise to do something or a formal statement that something is true. The TL term “oath” means swearing or conjuration. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep-Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) provides the equivalent term as swearing. So, it is optimum degree of translation and the translator has used literal translation technique.

Table 9: Social Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	āgyākāri	Tapāiko āgyākāri vāi (p.57)	Obedient	Your obedient brother him. (p.47)

Here, the term *āgyākāri* means dutifully complying with the commands or instructions of those in authority. *The Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary* (8th ed.) defines “obedient” as doing what you are told to do. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep-Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) also focuses on the matter of hearsomeness. So, it is optimum translation and translator has used literal technique of translation.

5.1.4 Religious Culture

Religious culture includes the terms about myths, religious beliefs, tradition, customs and name of gods. It also encompasses religious activities and places. Three religious terms selected from the novel '*Seto Bagh*' and their equivalent terms in English are described as below:

Table 10: Religious Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>Biswās</i>	<i>bābūle basāleko rajnitik āsthā rākhne janga vaiko vanāimābiswās parena. (p.98)</i>	Faith	Janga brothers could never agree with him for they had only faith on father. (p.83)

The SL word *biswās* is used for showing reliability in religious matter. The TL term “faith” means trust in somebody’s ability or knowledge. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep-Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) gives the equivalent term as faith. So, it is optimum translation and literal technique of translation is used.

Table 11: Religious Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>Nakshetra</i>	<i>Ye dūijanako kūn nakshetra namilekole blbāha jurena. (p.143)</i>	Planets	Whose planets wield negative influence on the horoscope of Bir and Princess. (p.113)

The word *nakshetra* means movement of seven main bodies that move relatively to fixed stars. The TL term “planet” means a large round object in space that moves around a star. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep- Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) gives the equivalent term as movement of stars. So, it is near optimum translation and sense translation technique has been used.

Table 12: Religious Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>Janmakūndali</i>	<i>Rajkanyāko dulahisaga janmak ūndali namilekale uhaharūko mūkh malIn vāyo. (p.139)</i>	horoscopes	Whose planets wield negative influence on the horoscope of Bir and Princess. (p. 113)

They were worried about Somnath’s negative pronouncement on the horoscopes.(p,117) The word *janmakūndali* means an astrological forecast of a person’s future based on such information. The TL term “horoscopes” means a description of what is going to somebody in the future based on the position of stars and the planets when the person was born. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep-Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) provides the equivalent term as horoscopes. So, it is optimum degree of translation and literal technique is used as a technique.

5.1.5 Conceptual Terms

Conceptual terms refer to the common system of language shared by the members of a society that are generally non-concrete and abstract in nature. These terms can be understood in the presence of definitions. Members of a society generally share the same thinking or perception which can be understood by the help of componential analysis. Ten conceptual terms selected from the novel *Seto Bagh* and their equivalent terms in English have been mentioned as below:

Table 13: Conceptual Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	Garibi	Shajyadi ra unko bibaha nahune karan garibi thiyo. (p.84)	Poverty	It was because of his poverty the princess did not want to marry to him. (p.71)

The SL term *garibi* means the condition of being poor. The TL term “poverty” means the state of being poor. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep-English Dictionary* (1st ed.) provides the equal term as poor quality. So, it is optimum translation and the translator has used literal translation.

Table 14: Conceptual Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>Bijaya</i>	<i>Satrū māthi bijaya p āes.</i> (p.7)	Vanquish	May you get the strength you need to vanquish your enemies. (p.7)

The SL term *bijay ā* means the act of defeating others by any way. The TL term “vanquish” means come out better in a competition, race or conflict. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep-Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) provides the equivalent term as victory. So, it is optimum translation and literal technique of translation has been used.

Table 15: Conceptual Term

S.N.	SL Term	SL Context	TL Term	TL Context
1.	<i>Prem</i>	<i>Kum Kum timilai prem bhaneko thaha chha?</i> (p. 26)	Love	Kum, do you know what love is? (p.22)

The SL term *prem* means affection. *The Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary* (8th ed.) defines “love” as a strong feeling of deep affection for somebody/something. *Ekta Comprehensive Nep-Eng Dictionary* (1st ed.) provides the equivalent term as love. So, it is optimum translation and literal technique of translation has been used by the translator to achieve optimum degree of translation by compensating gaps and using literal techniques.

5.2 Analysis of Frequency and Percentage of Techniques of Translation

As translation has become the necessary thing in the present day world, various techniques of translation should be used by the translator in order to make any piece of translation contextually faithful and comprehensible to the readers. The following table represents the frequency and percentage of techniques of translation used in translating cultural terms of this novel ‘*Seto Bagh*’ into the translated version ‘*The Wake of the White Tiger*’.

The Below table shows the techniques applied in the translation of the cultural terms of the novel. Among the nine techniques used in this translation process, literal translation as a technique is the most frequent one. To translate, it was used i.e. 48% was occupied by this technique. After that, sense technique of translation was followed by 26 %. Definition is the

third mostly used technique with 14%. Substitution and transliteration are the third most frequently used techniques with 6%.

Table 16: Frequency and Percentage of the Techniques of Translation (TOT)

S.N.	TOT	Percentage
1.	Literal	48%
2.	Sense	26%
3.	Substitution	6%
4.	Definition	14%
5	Transliteration	6%
Total		100%

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, on the basis of approximation of the TT goals with their SL goals, translation equivalence was grouped under six degrees in this research, but only five degrees were found. The optimum degree of equivalence was the highest in number (48%). Similarly, six techniques of translation were identified. Among them, literal translation was used mostly (48%). Finally, the contribution of the techniques for achieving the degrees of equivalence was studied whereas literal translation contribution was highest (83.33%) for optimum degree of translation.

This research was systematically studied and found out that the quality of translation can be measured by finding out by the parameters of six degrees of equivalence namely optimum translation, near optimum translation, partial translation, poor translation, zero equivalence and mistranslation. The translator used several techniques to preserve the cultural taste of the terms and among the five techniques used, literal technique contributed at high rate and deletion technique should be removed from the technique to achieve high translation equivalence and translation quality. Finally, the translated text must maintain the original flavor of the SLT and it should be readable for the TL readers.

About the Author

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